

PROBLEMS OF AFGHAN REFUGEE STUDENTS IN PAKISTAN AND SYRIAN REFUGEE STUDENTS IN TURKEY: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The study was designed to investigate the Academic problems of afghan refugee students in Pakistan and Syrian refugee students in Turkey targeting the largest refugee community worldwide, it was comparative analysis of the problems of refugee students of the two groups of refugees. investigation was casual comparative in nature, questionnaire with 4 point Likert scale was used to collect data. The population of the study consists of 332 Afghan Students, from Khubaib college Rumi Pakistan, 341 Syrian students, from UluslararasıEbuUbeydeAnadolu İmam Hatiplisesi, Turkey. The sample was consisting 205 Afghan refugee's school students in Pakistan and 203 students from Syrian refugee's school in Turkey by using Total population sampling or the purposive sampling technique. Data were analyzed by SSPS applying the Chi square test, T-test and Anova. The results reveals that the academic problems of Syrian Refugee students were more than Afghan refugee students. When considering the Academic problems comparison between and within the group it was concluded that there was a difference between both groups of refugee students. Refugee students may be provided with a language training program of sufficient duration before attending school in the host country and receive the same curriculum once they have overcome their language problems. Having diverse migration and educational backgrounds, the situation affects their educational and psychological requirements. Schools, teachers, parents, and the community may work together to support refugee pupils. These students' emotional and cultural needs must be met by teachers. Mentoring must be done proactively by teachers and guidance counselors in order to make it easier for refugee kids who have experienced difficulties. It was proposed that additional research be conducted in order to maintain the refugee education process and win the public's support.

Keywords: Problems, Afghan Refugee, Students, Pakistan, Syrian Refugee, Turkey, Comparative, Analysis

INTRODUCTION

Since the conclusion of the Cold War, there have been increased global refugee migrations. Both in Turkey and Afghanistan as well as other parts of the world, the refugee issue is getting worse. Particularly in recent years, political unrest, repression, and war have led to massive migration from the Middle East and South Asia. People from this region emigrate, notably to Pakistan and Turkey. In April 2011, Turkey accepted refugees

for the first time by adopting an unwavering "open door policy" toward civilians escaping the crisis in Syria. (Ahmadoun, 2014, Gul, R., Ahmad, I., Tahir, T., Ishfaq, U. (2022). Gul, R., Tahir, T. Ishfaq, U., Batool, S. 2021. Tahir, T, K. Khan, Aurangzeb, W. (2019). Due to its location, Turkey makes for a rather easy crossing point. However, when they arrived and settled in Turkey, they encountered some brand-new challenges. The education of their children is one of these challenges. Refugee pupils attend Turkish schools where they receive their education, where they encounter numerous difficulties. (Ahmadoun, 2014. Millions of Afghan refugees have taken refuge in Pakistan. International emigration from Afghanistan has a long history. The recent changes in Afghanistan led to successive waves of Afghan refugees fleeing their country for Pakistan. A new surge of migrants has recently arrived as a result of the quick American pullout from the nation and the Taliban takeover that followed. Over 59.5 million people, half of whom are children, are currently experiencing dislocation and displacement, according to the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees. This is the biggest number ever recorded, illustrating how the global human displacement crisis is a significant and growing problem for human growth, health, and education. These young people continue to experience several difficulties and daily tensions after arriving, including adjusting to a new social milieu, educational system, culture, and language, as well as coming to grips with historical atrocities and families going through change. (Fraine and McDade, 2009, (Gul, N., Tahir, T., Gul, R., Batool, S. 2022, Gul, R., Tahir., Ishfaq, U., Batool, T. 2021).

Less research has been done on how young refugees deal with the problems they encounter on a daily basis, despite the fact that there is a lot of research on the pressures and challenges young refugees face during resettlement. This study is exclusively designed to investigate the academic issues, and problems of refugees respectively in Pakistan and Turkey affected by the recent displacement waves. Moreover, by keeping in view the efforts made by both countries to facilitate their neighbor, a comparative analysis will be conducted to draw a clear picture of the situation. The total objective of the study is to compare the Problems of Afghan Refugee Students In Pakistan And research Refugee Students In Turkey.

Significance of The Study

The investigation may help the stakeholders to learn about the problems regarding academic problems of the refugees which they may face during and after migration to other countries. This study may shed some light on the pedagogical patterns of teaching such vulnerable segments of the world. This study may also provide guidelines to organizations whether governmental or nongovernmental, that there is a need for improvement regarding efforts that have been made to help these refugees.

Statement of The Problem

The study was planned to study the academic problems of refugee students in the host country's educational setups. Researcher selected the one school for Afghan refugee students from Pakistan and the second one from Turkey, a school for Syrian refugee students to compare the situation.

Research Questions

1. What academic problems are Syrian / Afghan refugee students experiencing during schooling in Turkey and Pakistan?
2. Is there any difference in academic problems faced by Syrian and Afghan Refugee students in Turkey and Pakistan?

Delimitations

The study was delimited only to Khubaib College Rumi, BabuChowk Sector No 04 Khalabut Town Ship Haripur Khyber Pukhtunkhawa Pakistan and UluslararasıEbuUbeydeAnadolu İmam Hatiplisesi, RehanliHatay, Turkey.

Research Design

The investigation was a casual comparative to evaluate the opinion of refugee students through the questionnaire. This study aims to study two different cultural groups in different settings. This method may help the researcher to collect data in less time and results could be generalized to a larger population across the world.

Population

The population of the study consists of 332 Afghan Students, from Khubaib College Rumi Pakistan, and 341 Syrian students, from UluslararasıEbuUbeydeAnadolu İmam Hatiplisesi, Turkey will be the population selected for the study.

Sample

The sample of the research consisted of 216 Afghan refugee school students in Pakistan and 220 students from a Syrian refugee school's students in Turkey were selected as sample of the study, the researcher excluded the peer school children from the whole population and took the rest of the number as a sample.

Research Tools

One comprehensive questionnaire was used for collecting data; the questionnaire covered the academic problems of Afghan refugee students in Pakistan and Syrian refugee students in Turkey respectively, consists of 18 items on 4 point Likert scale.

Data Collection

The data were collected from the sample schools through collaboration with the administration of schools. After the collection of the data and ensuring its authenticity it was analyzed. To analyze the data researcher used the, T. Test and ANOVA to analyze the data.

Ethical Clearance

Ethical approval was gained from the ethical committee "The University of Haripur Ethical Committee" Haripur, Pakistan. Consent has been taken from targeted Schools. Attention is paid to the ethical issue of privacy and dignity of those directly or indirectly involved

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

T-Test

Table 1: Comparison of academic problems

S	N	M	SD	SE Mean	Levine's Test Sig.	t	p	Cohen's d
Afghan	215	51.27	2.84	0.19	2.54	-3.73	0.00	0.363014
Syrian	211	52.33	3.00	0.20	0.11			

Table 1 shows that Afghan Students M 215(51.27), SD (2.84), SE Mean (0.19), Syrian Students M 211(52.33), SD (3.00), SE Mean (0.20) while Levine's Test 2.54(0.11), t (-3.73), p (0.00) cd (0.363014) $p < 0.05$ shows that the academic problems of Syrian are greater than Afghan students.

ANOVA

Table 2: Academic problems comparison between and within the group.

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
AP	Between Groups	125.938	3	41.979	4.910	0.002
	Within Groups	3607.883	422	8.549		
	Total	3733.822	425			

In Table 2 sum of squares (125.938), df 3, MS (41.979), within groups sum of squares (3607.883), df 425, MS (8.549), F (4.910) and Sig (0.002), $p < 0.05$ shows that difference between groups is significant.

Post Hoc Tests

Table 3: Multiple comparisons

(I) Level	(J) Level	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Afghan Middle	Afghan Secondary	0.03667	0.41152	0.929	-0.7722	0.8456
	Syrian Middle	-1.22603*	0.38211	0.001	-1.9771	-0.4750
	Syrian Secondary	-0.86595*	0.37908	0.023	-1.6111	-0.1208
Afghan Secondary	Syrian Middle	-1.26270*	0.43331	0.004	-2.1144	-0.4110
	Syrian Secondary	-0.90262*	0.43064	0.037	-1.7491	-0.0562
Syrian Middle	Syrian Secondary	0.36008	0.40263	0.372	-0.4313	1.1515

The above table indicates a difference in perceived academic problems between Afghan Middle and Afghan Secondary school students' MD (0.03667), Std. E (0.41152), p (0.929), $p > 0.05$ which shows that there is no significant difference. Afghan Middle and Syrian Middle MD (-1.22603*), Std. E (0.38211), Sig (0.023), $p < 0.05$ which shows that there is a significant difference. Afghan Middle and Syrian Secondary MD (-0.86595*), Std. E (0.37908), Sig (0.001), $p < 0.05$ which shows that there is a significant difference. Afghan Secondary and Syrian Middle MD (-1.26270*), Std. E (0.43331), Sig (0.004), $p < 0.05$ which shows that there is a significant difference. Afghan Secondary and Syrian Secondary MD (-0.90262*), Std. E (0.43064), Sig (0.037), $p < 0.05$ which shows that there

is a significant difference. Syrian Middle and Syrian Secondary MD (0.36008), Std. E (0.40263), Sig (0.372), $p > 0.05$ which shows that there is no significant difference.

DISCUSSION

The study investigated the academic, psychological and social problem problems of Afghan refugee students in Pakistan and Syrian refugee students in Turkey. The study was a casual comparative to evaluate the opinion of refugee students through the questionnaire. The t-test (comparing two means) was applied to illustrate the results of two groups of refugee students. Furthermore, to differentiate between and within group responses Post Hoc Tests were applied to get a clearer picture of the results. The Chi-Square results show that there was a significant difference between the responses of both groups about problems faced being refugees. These results are in line with Gömleksiz, (2018). A qualitative research design was employed in this study. The case study was taken from qualitative research designs. There are 16 refugee students in all, 14 of whom are contestants; one is from Iraq, and the other two are from Azerbaijan. The findings of the study showed that refugee kids encounter certain difficulties in Turkish schools for a variety of reasons, including the medium of instruction, the lack of parental support, school culture and customs, course content, and teaching methods and strategies. For refugee pupils, using smart boards and visual aids makes learning easier. On the other hand, they are incapable of understanding direct education methods, reading, or writing. The majority of refugee pupils report that their classmates are kind and supportive. They do, however, struggle a bit to adjust to school regulations. Some of them claim that their pals initially exhibited inappropriate behaviour. The majority of refugee students claim that their family support them financially and morally in their education, despite the fact that their parents are illiterate. As a result, they can't really assist with their assignments. Most refugee kids believe that they need to learn everything, especially science and math. Some of them believe that lessons in technology and design are unnecessary for them. While one-half of the refugee pupils believe they speak and listen properly in Turkish, the other one-half disagree. The teachings in science and mathematics they learned in their earlier schooling, according to half of the contributors, have a favorable impact on their current education. The other half believe that their earlier coursework has had no beneficial impact on their current education. The study's refugee students come from a variety of migration and educational backgrounds; some came to Turkey straight from their home country, while others first migrated to and remained in other countries before arriving in Turkey. Their emotional and educational needs are impacted by this disorder. (Mace, Mulheron, Jones and Cherian, 2014).

CONCLUSIONS

1. Regarding academic problems, it was concluded that Afghan students are more satisfied than Syrian students with the subject taught and teacher support provided. Both groups faced communication problems during the study period. However, guidance and help services were not sufficient in both institutions. By using

supporting materials, students could easily understand, which was helpful in their reading, writing and speaking tasks for both groups.

2. The setup of the schools in the host country while Syrian students showed satisfaction and meaning. While both groups agreed that financial support is available for their academics, they believe that the syllabus applied in the host country may affect their culture so there should be separate schools for the refugee community. Syrian students get moral support while Afghans. Afghan and Syrian students agreed with the opinion that subjects taught at the host country's schools are necessary. Moreover, Afghan students were not satisfied with our lack according to their responses, both groups are in demand of multilingual teachers in schools.
3. It was comprehensively concluded that the academic problems of Syrian Refugee students were more than Afghan refugee students. When considering the Academic problems comparison between and within the group it was concluded that there was a modification among both groups of refugee students.

Recommendations

1. On account of organization who are working for the education of refugee students it is recommended that while educational challenges are individual and personal, continuous and adequate academic, Financial, psychological and moral support may provide to refugee students to meet special challenges experienced by refugee students, along with potential parental support, facilitate their adjustment, and progress within the education and schooling system.
2. Refugee students may provide with a language training program of sufficient duration before attending school in the host country and receive the same curriculum once they have overcome their language problems.
3. The influx of refugee children and youth into countries where teachers are unprepared to assist the refugees and the rise in global migration brought on by conflict call for attention and action from governmental and non-governmental international organizations to take measures for teacher education and professional development to prepare them to teach refugees. This might make it possible for instructors to create culturally sensitive teaching.

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